

ETHNODIDACTICS: APPLYING ANTHROPOLOGY TO THE TEACHING OF A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN MIGRATORY CONTEXTS

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Abstract

The article presents an experimental didactic approach, termed ethnodidactic, applied to teaching a foreign language in multicultural school contexts. This approach integrates the principles of communicative didactics with those of anthropology, making use of the ethnographic method as a tool for both research and the conduct of the lesson. The experiment took place in 2024/2025 at a CPIA in Lombardy, involving adult migrant students with different levels of schooling, including illiterate students. The core of the model consists of the autonomous production of materials (images, videos, objects, gestures), through which students communicate personal experiences, which are then translated and re-elaborated into the target language. This reversal of the classic model, where it is usually the teacher who provides the content, enables active participation and enhances prior knowledge, creating an inclusive and motivating environment. In an ethnodidactic perspective, the learner is not merely a recipient but becomes an active resource and a source of linguistic material. Language teaching is thus grounded in the activation of an authentic communicative need, intentionally elicited by the teacher through the introduction of meaningful topics capable of generating biographical and emotional engagement. This need triggers a narrative process of autobiographical sharing, building bridges between proposed content and personal experience. The result is the creation of authentic linguistic materials—oral and visual texts—that reflect the cultural and linguistic complexity of the classroom. The teacher assumes a maieutic role, fostering relational spaces and offering tools for metalinguistic reflection, while the learner becomes the central figure in the language acquisition process through their own narrative. In this way, the classroom transforms into an intercultural and dialogic laboratory where language is constructed starting from the self and in relation to others, within a continuous dynamic of identity, alterity, and learning. This strategy was observed to transform the class into a relational community, akin to a family environment, where language comprehension arises from the desire to tell one's story, share, and be understood. Aligned with the communicative approach to language teaching, the proposed model goes beyond even the most advanced instructional recommendations, favoring a learning environment where language serves as a vehicle for communication and a tool for expressing one's self and worldview. In this framework, the teacher's role overlaps with that of the ethnographer, who, adopting an anthropological posture—centered on active listening, decentering, and valuing the other's perspective—observes classroom dynamics and participates as a facilitator (Mussi, 2022). The experimentation showed that this approach not only achieves the aforementioned objectives but also fosters a learning environment guided by an intercultural logic.

Keywords: ethnodidactics; CPIA; storytelling; images and videos; language teaching; flipped classroom; intercultural education; education of migrant adults; inclusion.

INTRODUCTION

This paper proposes an experimental educational approach, which we define as *ethnodidactic*, for the teaching of L2/FL (second or foreign language) in multicultural school settings. The term itself merges elements of both ethnography and language didactics, combining the principles of the communicative approach to second language teaching with those of the ethnographic method—recognized as a core investigative tool within the discipline of anthropology.

The first experimental implementation took place during the 2024/2025 academic year at the *Centro Provinciale per l'Istruzione degli Adulti* (CPIA) of Monza, in a class composed of adult migrant learners with diverse linguistic and educational backgrounds, including individuals experiencing illiteracy or limited formal schooling. In Italy, the CPIAs—public institutions dedicated to adult education—have operated in their current form since 2015¹. These centers focus primarily on educating adults with migratory backgrounds. The experimental project was conducted at a CPIA located in the city of Monza, in northern Italy, where students - though all over the age of sixteen - differ in age and predominantly originate from North Africa, sub-Saharan Africa, and Latin America. Migration dynamics in Italy have brought renewed attention to the issue of illiteracy, now complicated by an added layer of complexity: unlike in the past, those in need of literacy instruction are often learners who do not speak Italian as their first language and who possess only basic communicative competence, frequently as newly arrived individuals². In such a complex context, L2 instruction presents significant challenges—not only in terms of language acquisition but also with respect to relationship-building, motivation, and social inclusion. The proposed approach seeks to address these needs by integrating communicative language teaching principles with anthropological research methodologies. Central to the educational process are autobiographical narrative, active listening, and participatory learning.

This contribution presents the outcomes of the experimental project, detailing the strategies employed and the observed results. The findings suggest that this approach is both effective and replicable in highly complex educational contexts. The experimentation was jointly carried out by the authors—teachers of Italian as a second language at the CPIA of Monza and Brianza—who brought together complementary expertise: on the one hand, specific training in anthropology; on the other, extensive experience in adult literacy education.

1. ANTHROPOLOGY AND EDUCATION: THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The anthropology of education today offers new interpretative lenses within school contexts (Simonicca, 2018), enabling the investigation—both in a comparative and diachronic manner—of dynamics emerging in educational settings. A paradigmatic example is the renowned study by Joseph Tobin on early childhood education in China, Japan, and the United States (Tobin, 2011). Numerous international studies have already highlighted the effectiveness of ethnography as a qualitative research tool capable of capturing, in depth, the interactions and inclusion processes within educational contexts (Hammersley, 2006; Tassan, 2024). In Italy, recent research such as that conducted by Alessandra Mussi (2023) has applied anthropological methodology to amplify the voices of Arabic-speaking women engaged in L2 Italian language learning, revealing the multifaceted nature of migrant parenthood. Anthropology has long been recognized as possessing intrinsic educational value (Tim Ingold). Francesca Gobbo, a leading scholar in intercultural education, advocates for rethinking teacher education through the lens of the “teacher-ethnographer.” This figure is characterized by the adoption of fieldwork-inspired postures, including:

- The construction of an *ethnographic relationship* with students, grounded in gradual access, relational care, and intercultural sensitivity;
- The use of biographical approaches that emphasize giving voice to the “subaltern”;

¹ Adult education in Italy has undergone profound transformations in response to the country's economic and social changes. Starting in the 1980s, with the onset of what Colucci (2023) refers to as the “era of migrations,” and with Italy—like many other European countries—transitioning from a country of emigration to one of immigration (Castles, De Haas, Miller, 2014), the presence of foreign students has become increasingly significant, to the point that they now constitute the predominant group within the CPIA (Provincial Centres for Adult Education).

² After the fall of Fascism and the birth of the Italian Republic, illiteracy was officially recognized by the government as a social issue requiring intervention (Targhetta, 2015). Testimonies from current CPIA teachers who taught in workers' education courses during the 1990s in the Brianza area (now the CPIA of Monza) reveal that, for a long time, adult education—then organized around the “150-hour” program—was primarily attended by Italian citizens who were illiterate or had low levels of schooling, often originating from southern regions and having migrated northward during the period of internal migration toward the industrialized North.

o The adoption of a method that is rigorous yet flexible, capable of analyzing macro, meso, and micro perspectives and of adapting pedagogical planning accordingly (Gobbo, 2004).

The innovative aspect at the core of the proposed approach lies in the use of participant observation—central to the ethnographic method—not only as a research tool, but also as an epistemological and relational posture that shapes the conduct of didactic activities in second or foreign language teaching. It takes the form of a set of guidelines that are simultaneously operational and conceptual-theoretical, designed to inform and support pedagogical action. From this perspective, both language didactics and anthropology are not limited to providing theoretical frameworks; they actively influence educational practices, transforming the way teachers relate to their students. The teacher who adopts an anthropological posture conceives the classroom as a field of research, identifying a specific focus of observation within it and assuming the role of *participant observer*. This leads to a reversal of the traditional glottodidactic paradigm: the primary focus is no longer solely on language itself—although it remains a key medium of communication—but rather on mutual recognition, relational engagement, and the possibility of self-narration. The classroom thus becomes a space for shared exploration, where listening, storytelling, and participation are integral to the teaching practice.

2. GLOTTODIDACTICS: THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The ethnodidactic approach proposes a reorganization of the teaching-learning process through a strategic inversion of traditional roles. In the initial phase, the teacher introduces selected discussion topics and invites students to autonomously prepare expository materials using a range of communicative modalities—images, videos, objects, gestures—in order to overcome expressive limitations in the target language. The learner thus becomes both observer and observed, narrator and protagonist of their own educational journey.

In this process, the teacher assumes the role of *semiotic mediator*, translating into the target language the communicative intent conveyed through the students' diverse expressive modes. This didactic process represents an original reinterpretation of *Augmentative and Alternative Communication (AAC)*³, but operates in a reversed logic: while traditional AAC involves transforming verbal language into images, the ethnodidactic model begins with images, gestures, and visual narratives as a foundation for the construction of linguistic competence (Beukelman & Mirenda, 2013).

This generates authentic and meaningful communicative needs, as the materials produced by the students—images, videos, objects, and narratives—are not confined to private use but are shared within the classroom community. The shift from “individual production” to a “learning community” creates a dialogic space that fosters an inclusive climate in which every participant is granted the opportunity for self-representation and recognition in their uniqueness.

The subsequent methodological phase involves the systematization of linguistic structures that emerged during the semiotic mediation. The transition from intersemiotic translation to verbal formulation is realized through the identification and selection of *lexical chunks*—cognitive units that facilitate efficient information processing and memorization (Miller, 1956; Gobet et al., 2001). In the proposed methodology, these elements do not originate from arbitrary selection, but emerge organically from the semantic content conveyed through students' iconic representations. The teacher's selection of linguistic structures is guided by cognitive psychology principles related to chunking, which enhances language acquisition by grouping information into manageable units.

The memorization of linguistic formulas within the ethnodidactic framework is grounded in the principles of *implicit learning* (Ellis, 2005) and the *usage-based theory of language acquisition* (Tomasello, 2003). These structures, anchored in the student's expressive experience through multimodal supports, are internalized through *semantic-pragmatic association* rather than mechanical repetition. The “natural” character of this memorization process lies in its contextualized and meaningful nature. As Wray (2002) has demonstrated in her work on *formulaic sequences*, the acquisition of pre-assembled lexical blocks is a fundamental cognitive strategy in second language learning, particularly effective when such sequences are tied to authentic

³ Augmentative and Alternative Communication (AAC) is a set of strategies and tools designed to facilitate communication in individuals with complex communication needs. In traditional practice, AAC starts from verbal language and associates it with images, symbols, or signs that enhance comprehension or support production. It is, therefore, a process that moves from words to images, using visual aids to reinforce or substitute spoken language. (Beukelman, D. R., & Mirenda, P. (2013). *Augmentative and Alternative Communication: Supporting Children and Adults with Complex Communication Needs* (4th ed.). Paul H. Brookes Publishing Co.)

communicative experiences.

The acquisition of formulaic language constitutes a natural learning strategy that allows learners to store a set of ready-to-use linguistic structures applicable to analogous communicative situations (Ellis, 2008; Wray, 2002). This formulaic approach proves especially effective for low-schooled adult learners, as it mirrors mechanisms typical of natural first language acquisition and does not require metalinguistic skills (Minuz, 2005). It is even more effective with pre-literate learners, who tend to develop cognitive strategies grounded in situational and contextual thinking (Cole, 1981; Street, 1984). This type of cognition—widely documented in cultural psychology and educational research—is characterized by direct anchoring in concrete experience, contrasting with the symbolic abstraction typical of literate cultures. Research has shown that non-literate minds favor information processing strategies rooted in the tangible and contextual, which this didactic approach aims to activate and value in practice (Luria, 1976; Olson, 1994). Both literate and non-literate students follow the same linguistic acquisition processes.

The proposed strategy generates a level playing field by placing schooled and illiterate learners on the same operational level. On the one hand, in the target language both groups share similar limitations in oral competence; on the other hand, the necessary recourse to multi-modal communicative tools activates transversal competences that go beyond traditional literacy. The result is a learning environment where formal schooling is not an advantage, but where all participants develop inclusive communicative strategies. The approach valorises forms of intelligence and competence that transcend the literate/illiterate dichotomy, configuring the classroom as a truly democratic learning space in which different forms of knowledge and modes of expression find legitimacy and equal development.

Thematic selection—central to lesson development in the ethnodidactic approach—emerges organically from classroom interaction. This bottom-up content definition process is in line with fieldwork principles, in which the researcher's attention is directed toward what spontaneously surfaces in the observed context (Clifford & Marcus, 1986). Students themselves often suggest topics for further exploration through spontaneous references or curious questions. Within this dialogic paradigm, the teacher also becomes a narrator, sharing personal experiences in a comparative logic. A meaningful example of this dynamic occurred during a lesson when an interreligious dialogue emerged spontaneously and engaged the entire class. Each student attempted to explain their personal experience of the topic. In the following session, student Sillah—one of the pre-literate learners—spontaneously requested the projection of a self-produced video in which he was the protagonist. In the video, he visually demonstrated, primarily through action, the preparatory steps he takes before prayer. The footage showed him performing ablutions, which sparked a lively discussion that prompted other students to create additional audiovisual materials documenting everyday religious practices in their home environments. This episode clearly illustrates how the ethnodidactic approach allows the emergence of highly meaningful content for learners content that would likely not have been included in a traditional curriculum. At this stage, the teacher's role includes observing and reflecting not only on the emergent content but also on how learners select, prioritize, and present aspects of their cultures they consider most meaningful to share with their peers. The *exposition phase* becomes central: learners are invited to present their chosen topic using their full communicative repertoire—previously acquired Italian vocabulary, gestures, images, videos, and personal objects brought from home (Kress & van Leeuwen, 2001). The iconic materials presented by the learners convey complex meanings and enable the sharing of experiences that would otherwise be difficult to express through oral language alone. In summary, the structure of each lesson unfolds through sequential phases: *active listening* to the student's multimodal production; *interpretation* of meanings conveyed through various communicative channels; *reformulation* in the target language; and *analysis* of the linguistic structures that have emerged. It is essential that the teacher refrains from imposing predetermined translations, instead guiding learners in discovering the correspondence between *signifier* and *meaning* in the elements presented during their expositions and in the teacher's translations. The subsequent objective is the *active reuse* of the acquired linguistic structures and vocabulary. Students are encouraged to apply these elements in different communicative situations, adapting them to their expressive needs. This dynamic gives rise to individual reformulation strategies, which in turn inform the design of increasingly targeted and personalized teaching interventions.

3. FROM THE FIELD DIARY⁴

To make explicit the operational dimension of the proposed approach, we have chosen to include an excerpt

⁴ The field diary is a typical tool used by anthropologists to observe and describe situations, contexts, and interactions, with the aim of later developing theoretical reflections based on lived experience.

from the field diary that accompanied the experimental teaching activities. The resulting ethnographic account documents not only the development of the teaching activities, but also highlights how the adopted approach contributes to transforming a heterogeneous group of individuals into a learning community shaped by an intercultural logic. The class that served as the field for research and experimentation belonged to the youngest age group at the CPIA, consisting of students aged between 16 and 25, who had recently arrived in Italy. It was a heterogeneous group in terms of educational and personal background, with very different levels of schooling, including two students who were illiterate. The participants came from several countries: Senegal, Gambia, Ivory Coast, Morocco, Egypt, Sri Lanka, Brazil, China, and Kosovo.

3.1 Ethnographic tale – January 9, 2025⁵

An opportunity for discussion arose during an afternoon lesson when the Muslim call to prayer suddenly echoed through the classroom. The sound came from M.'s cellphone, and after a brief moment of hesitation, she lowered the volume. The moment proved to be a valuable opportunity to explain the meaning of the sound and to contextualize it. Given the students' different religious backgrounds, not everyone knew that there is a specific call to prayer for Muslims. I played the sound of church bells for the class, pointing out that Christianity also has its own form of prayer call. Using the interactive whiteboard, I explained how the number and rhythm of bell chimes can vary, signaling either a joyful event or a funeral. The students appeared surprised and interested, as they had heard church bells before but had never had a chance to understand their meaning.

This episode became a pretext for expanding vocabulary and language structures. The emergent structures, paired with words like “bell,” “bell tower,” “church,” “funeral,” “celebration,” “prayer,” “call,” were linked to some useful language chunks: “this is a small church”; “this is a large mosque”; “this church has a bell tower”; “this is the sound of the bells”; “this is the call to prayer”; “in a mosque you pray barefoot”; “in a church you pray without a hat.” These linguistic structures were contextualized and used in conversation. Finally, the class collaboratively wrote down the sentences that had emerged during oral interaction, thereby reinforcing the connection between orality and writing.

A collective reflection emerged on the variety of religious affiliations in the group: students of African origin declared themselves mostly Muslim, except for Zogbo, who is an evangelical Christian; students from Sri Lanka and the Chinese student identified as Buddhist. On the same day, still on the topic of religions, Nethmi approached the teacher's desk with a USB stick in hand, expressing a desire to share a presentation about her religion, which is Buddhism. Her autonomous initiative was welcomed enthusiastically, and her presentation, supported by slides, became a further opportunity for collective learning. The student showed images of an important procession that takes place in Kandy, Sri Lanka, in August, where dozens of adorned elephants parade through the streets. One of them carries a sacred relic: a tooth of the Buddha. Nethmi's story sparked curiosity among her classmates, especially among Muslim students, who asked many questions: “Is Buddha God?” “Is that God's tooth?” Once again, the comparison of personal experiences required an intercultural approach. Interest also extended to the ritual dimension, with a description of sacred dances, drums, and ceremonial practices.

This episode also led to vocabulary expansion. The emergent structures, paired with words like “drums,” “barefoot men,” “elephants,” “music and dance,” were linked to chunks such as: “this is the sound of a drum”; “these are barefoot men”; “Sillah walks barefoot in the mosque”; “these men dance barefoot.” These structures were used in conversation and were later collaboratively written down, reinforcing the bond between spoken and written language. It was precisely this lesson that inspired Sillah to create a video in which he explained to the class the ablution practices related to his religion. This is the same video mentioned in the previous paragraph, born from a spontaneous initiative of the student as an active response to the intercultural dialogue that had emerged in the classroom.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The experiment conducted at the CPIA in Monza demonstrated the effectiveness of the ethnodidactic approach in teaching a foreign language to adult students from diverse cultural backgrounds, highlighting its potential because it:

- facilitates a significant lowering of affective filters, resulting in the formation of a cohesive class group—an essential condition for the spontaneous acquisition of language (Krashen, 1985);

⁵ The italicized sections are transcriptions from the field diary.

- promotes learning mechanisms typical of informal environments—where practical experience and personal engagement are central—by transposing them into formal school contexts (Rivoltella, 2013). Materials spontaneously presented by students—such as objects, stories, or videos—spark a genuine desire for communication and dialogue, characteristic of informal exchanges, thereby making learning more meaningful and participatory;
- enables an understanding of each student's life experiences, fostering personalized teaching that can identify and value the individual competences of every learner (Porcaro, 2020);
- allows the teacher-ethnographer to capture student representations and the relational dynamics within the class (Hall, 1997). Through the field diary, significant observations can be gathered to support a continuous process of reflexivity and self-reflection—both regarding the teacher's role and the transformation of the class into a learning community. This is accompanied by a metadidactic reflection aimed at qualitatively improving language lessons, in which critical observation of interactions and produced materials becomes a tool for educational reworking and innovation.

It has been observed that ethnodidactic lessons transform the classroom into a relational community, akin to a family, where language comprehension arises from the desire to tell one's story, share, and be understood. The approach refers to—and goes beyond—the flipped classroom strategy, which reverses the didactic axis: it is not the teacher who provides prepackaged language materials, but the students who produce content—photos, drawings, short videos, and recordings—which are then shared and analyzed collectively in class. These materials, created independently or in small groups, become privileged vehicles of meaning: they express a way of being in and inhabiting the world. From them, lexical and syntactic discoveries emerge, as well as a deeper understanding of the students' lived experiences. Based on this material, a didactic environment is built upon mutual discovery, dialogue, and comparison. Language learning becomes a process of shared decoding: the images and videos produced by the students themselves activate a collective exploration of the language and of each individual's life story, allowing functional vocabulary and basic grammatical structures to emerge spontaneously and meaningfully. The approach has proven particularly suitable in contexts marked by discontinuities in education and high biographical and cultural diversity. It is based on a flexible and adaptive idea of teaching, capable of valuing the communicative skills already possessed by students—even if not formally expressed—and of stimulating motivation through the recognition of one's voice in the school context. Language is thus learned as a living, functional tool in the service of storytelling, relationships, and citizenship. Consequently, assessment is conceived as a process of continuous observation and shared reflection; it becomes an integral part of the teaching and learning experience, helping to reveal individual progress, communicative strategies, forms of cooperation, and participation. A process-oriented and personal-growth-oriented assessment model is preferred, in line with the centrality given to experience and narration. From this perspective, in which the student is an active part of the teaching process, involving them in the evaluation phase—through self-assessment and co-assessment practices—can be particularly meaningful, fostering awareness of one's path and encouraging a reflective and responsible attitude toward learning.

In conclusion, the approach tested constitutes a concrete proposal for addressing foreign language teaching in highly complex migratory contexts in an innovative and inclusive way. The replicability of the approach in other similar educational settings represents a development opportunity that deserves further exploration and experimentation.

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